

Review article about Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

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Abstract:

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a medical imaging technique that uses a magnetic field and computer-generated radio waves to create detailed images of the organs and tissues in your body. MRI is a noninvasive way for a medical professional to examine the organs, tissues and skeletal system. It produces high-resolution images of the inside of the body that help diagnose a variety of conditions. Because MRI doesn't use X-rays or other radiation, it's the imaging test of choice when people will need frequent imaging for diagnosis or treatment monitoring, especially of their brain.

Keywords: *Magnetic resonance imaging, noninvasive diagnostics, computer-generated radio waves.*

Introduction

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

MRI is an imaging test that uses a magnetic field and computer-generated radio waves to create detailed images of organs and tissues inside the body.

Most MRI machines are large, cylindrical magnets. When you lie inside the MRI machine, the magnetic field inside the machine works with radio waves and hydrogen atoms in your body to create cross-sectional images that resemble slices of bread.

Each image looks like a slice taken through your body. The computer can also create a three-dimensional picture of the inside of your body. Unlike computed tomography (CT) and

positron emission tomography (PET), MRI does not use X-rays (radiation).

Because no X-rays or radiation are used, MRI is usually very safe.

MRI usually provides more detail than CT, but it takes longer and is more uncomfortable.

Because MRI uses a strong magnetic field, you cannot have it if you have certain types of metal in your body.

Most MRI machines require you to be placed in a narrow channel, so some people who are very anxious (claustrophobic) cannot have the test.

Some MRI machines have larger openings so that they do not cause as much discomfort to people.

Components of the MRI

The MRI system consists of four main components: a main magnet consisting of superconducting coils, gradient coils, radio frequency (RF) coils, and computer systems (Haralick, & Shanmugam, 1973). The following is a detailed explanation of the components of the MRI device:

1. The main magnet: The early MRI magnetic system mainly used the structure of magnetic sheets, the use of large quantities of magnetic sheets makes the weight and size of the system relatively large and the installation costs of the system high, with the rapid development of magnet technologies.

2. Gradient coils: The gradient coil set is an important component in a standard MRI scanner that produces linear gradient magnetic fields that are superimposed over a strong uniform magnetic field, and the uniform magnetic field is produced by a main magnet, which is aligned with the direction of proton motion. The superimposed gradient magnetic field slightly changes the frequency or phase of the proton motion, thus encoding the spatial information of an imaged object into the frequency associated with a location in space, in general, the gradient of the magnetic field generated by the gradient coils should be as linear as possible. A well-designed gradient coil should have low inductance, low resistance, high efficiency, etc., which is especially important in high-field imaging and fast imaging when all coil parameters must be highly optimized.

3. RF coil: The RF coil is the main component of the MRI system, acting as a transmitter as well as a receiver in forming the final images. There are different types of RF coils, and the difference between the coils lies in their use for different parts of the human body and different field strengths (Mokji, & Abu Bakar, 2007). According to the imaging of a part of the human body, they can be classified into head coils, body coils, knee coils, foot coils, etc. No matter how many types of coils there are, all coils can basically be treated as two types of coils, namely surface coils and volume coils (Mokji, & Abu Bakar, 2007). For surface coils, whose shape is

usually a circle, which facilitates the manufacture of the coil, they are often used as receivers. The reason is that the field they produce is inhomogeneous, which is detrimental to the imaging process. However, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of surface coils is higher than that of volume coils, partly because they can be placed close to the imaging area. At present, there is no Surface coils alone are used for receiving purpose. A group of surface coils, which we call a ring array, is used for its good performance in both receiving and transmitting.

History of Magnetic Resonance Imaging

The history of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) includes the work of many researchers who contributed to the discovery of nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and described the basic physics of MRI, beginning in the early 20th century. MRI was invented by Paul C. Lauterbur who developed a mechanism for encoding spatial information into an NMR signal using magnetic field gradients in September 1971; he published the theory behind it in March 1973. The factors that lead to image contrast (differences in tissue relaxation time values) were described almost 20 years earlier by the physician and scientist Erik Odblad and Gunnar Lindström. Among many other researchers in the late 1970s and 1980s, Peter Mansfield improved the techniques used to acquire and process MRI images, and in 2003 he and Lauterbur were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine for their contributions to the development of MRI. The first clinical MRI scanners were installed in the early 1980s and the technology has evolved greatly in the decades since, leading to its widespread use in medicine today.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

In 1950, Erwin Hahn first discovered spin resonances and free induction decays and in 1952, Herman Carr produced a one-dimensional NMR spectrum as reported in his doctoral thesis at Harvard University.

Machine of Magnetic Resonance

A scanner or MRI machine is a tube surrounded by a giant magnetic field. Where:

The patient is placed on a moving bed and inserted into the magnetic tube.

The magnet creates a strong magnetic field where protons from hydrogen atoms meet, and then a beam of radio waves is exposed to them.

A signal is produced that helps it to be detected by a receiver which is part of the MRI machine.

The information is processed by a computer, and an image is produced.

The resulting image is good as it reveals changes and small details of the body's structure, and for some procedures, radioactive materials, such as gadolinium, are used to increase the resolution of the images.

MRI takes 20 to 60 minutes, depending on the number of images required and the organ being imaged. The patient should also avoid movement as much as possible during the imaging time because movement affects the quality of the image. Therefore, MRI does not begin until the patient is fully prepared, and communication between the patient and the imaging technician takes place via an internal microphone to ensure his readiness. In some cases, the MRI time is long, allowing the patient to take a break after a certain period of time.

Types and Forms of Magnetic Resonance Imaging

The types of magnetic resonance imaging are:

Short-bore MRI, the body is outside the device and only the part to be imaged is inserted into the device.

Open MRI, in this system the device is open from all directions and this helps in capturing images for:

People with claustrophobia, which is a fear of closed spaces.

People who suffer from morbid obesity.

The next step (from spectra to imaging) was proposed by Vladislav Ivanov in the Soviet Union, who in 1960 filed a patent application for an MRI device. Ivanov's main contribution was the idea of using a magnetic field gradient, combined with frequency-selective excitation/readout, to encode spatial coordinates. In modern terms, it was proton density imaging (not relaxation times), which was also slow, as it used only one gradient direction at a time and imaging had to be done slice by slice. However, it was a real MRI procedure. Ivanov's application was originally rejected as unlikely, and Ivanov's application was finally approved in 1984 (with the original priority date).

Relaxation times and early development of MRI

By 1959, Jay Singer had studied blood flow by nuclear magnetic resonance relaxation time measurements of blood in living humans. Such measurements were not introduced into common medical practice until the mid-1980s, although a whole-body NMR device for measuring blood flow in the human body was patented by Alexander Janssen in early 1967

In the 1960s, the results of work on the relaxation, diffusion, and chemical exchange of water in cells and tissues of various types appeared in the scientific literature. In 1967, Lejeune reported the measurement of water relaxation by nuclear magnetic resonance in the arms of living humans. In 1968, Jackson and Langham published the first nuclear magnetic resonance signals from a living animal, an anesthetized rat.

In the 1970s, it was realized that relaxation times were the main determinants of contrast in MRI and could be used to detect and differentiate a range of diseases. A number of research groups showed that early cancer cells tended to exhibit longer relaxation times than their corresponding normal cells, thus stimulating the initial interest in the idea of detecting cancer using NMR. These early groups include Damadian, Hazelwood, Chang, and several others. This also began a program to catalog the relaxation times of a wide range of biological tissues, which

became one of the main drivers of the development of MRI.

Pancreas.

Uterus.

Ovaries.

Prostate.

MRI of bones and joint

MRI can help detect:

Joint problems caused by physical or repetitive trauma, such as torn cartilage or ligaments.

Disk problems in the spine.

Bone infections.

Bone and soft tissue tumors.

Breast MRI

MRI can be used with mammography to detect breast cancer, especially in women who have dense breast tissue or who may be at high risk for breast cancer

Uses of MRI:

1. MRI is used as a very accurate means of detecting diseases throughout the body. The uses of MRI depend on the area to be imaged, as:

MRI of the head, enables the doctor to look at the brain after trauma, bleeding, or swelling, and can image aneurysms in the brain and diagnose stroke and brain tumors, as well as tumors or inflammation in the upper part of the spine.

2. MRI of the back, used to assess the integrity of the spinal cord after trauma and accidents, and is also used when looking at problems associated with the vertebrae of the spine.

3. MRI of the heart, evaluates the structure of the heart and aorta, where aneurysms can be detected.

4. MRI of the abdomen, provides valuable information about the glands and organs inside the abdomen.

5. MRI of the joints and bones, provides accurate information about the structure of the joints, soft tissues, and bones in the body.

6. Magnetic resonance imaging is used to detect many cardiovascular problems, the most important of which are the following:

The size of the heart chambers.

The thickness of the heart walls.

Aneurysms.

Damage resulting from heart attacks.

Vascular infections.

Blood vessel blockages.

Using magnetic resonance imaging to detect tumors

7. Magnetic resonance imaging is used to detect tumors or abnormalities in:

Kidneys.

Liver.

Spleen.

Uterus.

Pancreas.

Ovaries.

Prostate

How to Prepare for an MRI

Before your MRI, eat your meals as you normally would and continue taking your regular medications unless you're told otherwise. You'll usually be asked to change into a gown and remove items that might interfere with the MRI, such as:

Jewelry.

Hairpins.

Eyeglasses.

Watches.

Wigs.

Dental dentures.

Hearing aids.

Bras with metal frames.

Makeup that contains metal particles.

During the Test

The MRI machine looks like a long, narrow tube that's open on both sides. You lie on a movable table that slides into the opening of the tube. A technologist watches you from another room. You can talk to the technologist through a microphone.

If you have a fear of tight spaces, known as claustrophobia, you may be given medicine to help you feel sleepy and reduce anxiety. Most patients get through the test without difficulty.

An MRI machine creates a strong magnetic field around you and beams radio waves into your body. The procedure is painless. You won't feel the magnetic field or radio waves, and there won't be anything moving around you.

During an MRI, the inside of the magnet makes repetitive sounds that sound like ticking, thumping, and so on. Wearing earplugs or listening to audio can help block out these lights.

In some cases, a contrast material, usually gadolinium, will be injected into a vein (IV) in your hand or arm. The contrast material helps clarify some details. Rarely, gadolinium can cause allergic reactions.

An MRI scan can last from 15 minutes to more than an hour. You must remain still because movement can blur the images.

During an fMRI scan, you may be asked to perform some simple tasks, such as pressing your thumb against the rest of your fingers, rubbing a piece of sandpaper, or answering simple questions. This helps identify the parts of the brain that control these actions.

Results

After the examination, the patient is given images of the area that was scanned, in addition to a report explaining the details of the case, which is presented to the treating physician to determine the appropriate treatment for the case.

Conclusion

In this study concluded that It produces high-resolution images of the inside of the body that help diagnose a variety of conditions. Because MRI doesn't use X-rays or other radiation, it's the imaging test of choice when people will need frequent imaging for diagnosis or treatment monitoring, especially of their brain.

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